

MAGNETO-OPTIC PHENOMENA AND MAGNETO-OPTICS OF SOLIDS.

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Abstract. In addition to the analysis of the literature, the article presents the main concepts used in the expression of physical processes, in particular, the axes of symmetry in the crystallographic structure, the review and drawings of the axes of symmetry of solid bodies, the importance of Miller's indices and their importance in expressing the parameters of solid bodies, especially magnetic ones, the theoretical basis of the magnetic ordering of crystals, electronic structures , shells, ferromagnets, antiferromagnets and ferrite substances, physical description of their formation conditions, domain boundaries in ferrites and their formation, structures of domain structures, magneto-optical phenomena and solids , magneto-optics, interaction of magnetic and optical departments comments have been given about the significance of the connection in the current modern technological development.

Keywords: electronic structures, shells, ferromagnets, antiferromagnets , ferrite substances , domain structures .

Humanity light and optical events with much long from the deadline since familiar Magnetism is one how many from centuries since to us familiar field is old in China magnet from stones known direction in orientation used Optics and magnetism of the fields to each other dependence first impressions about appear to be while not so much long time that it was no . XIX century in the middle (1845) English scientist M. Faraday by conducted in experiments this two field between

mutually dependence found out , that's it with together new field magneto-optics the first step in the field thrown away¹

Faraday known as the effect this to the effect according to , light or electromagnetic wave from substance pass during system external magnet to the field placed , of light polarization plane will change . For example initially vertical polarized light light external magnet in the field standing from substance when it passed polarization plane some kind of corner changes , this corner Faraday is called the corner , it is external magnet area , type of magnetic material depends.

First approach a magnet is a photon is called crystal . In this magnet plonks periodic placed is done , for example initially magnetic material layer , then magnet layer of non- material again magnet layer and etc. , so in sequence one how many ten layer replaced placing will be released . This is it prepared in the material Faraday and Kerr effects resonance increase observation can Second approach plasma cover using done is increased . In this magnet substance nanostructured metals with (gold , silver). will be combined . This is it prepared in combination Faraday and Kerr effects resonance increase observation can That's it emphasizing transition should be one sexual to substances than special structural in substances magneto-optical of effects one how many ten equal to increase observed .

This is it magneto-optical effects using external magnet on the field placed of substance properties changed without polarization plane or of light intensity change opportunity appear will be And this own in turn magneto-optical effects using different wave in length signals harvest make , modulate and again work enable will give . For this reason this effects of values to strengthen has been affairs continue even now reached is coming

¹ <http://youtu.be/x3mKzgCSBYo> . Sovremennaya magnetooptika - Vladimir Belotelov.

Magneto-optical of effects the following in the fields wide scale use can ²:

- in semiconductors charge of carriers effective mass and concentration determination ;
- of semiconductors zoned structures in learning ;
- optical contact in the lines laser its rays amplitude modulation ;
- optical not connected elements preparation ;
- molecules structure study
- ferromagnet of films domain structures study
- information magneto-optical writing get and use

Above showing passed fields of magneto-optics all " opening up " the possibilities does not give ". Faraday from the effect ionized of gas magnet area and interstellar in space space electrons it is also used in learning . Various in the states magneto-optical holographs on different studies is being held through while in computer science information three measured writing get and storage opportunity appear is happening Faraday and another magneto-optical to effects has been interest especially of nanophotonics appear from being after more increased .

This in chapter one how many magneto-optical of processes physicist features and to himself typical aspects statement we will try to do .

Faraday effect : 19th century second by half come whole the world physicists for new field doors opened . Faraday in 1845 come of physics yet mutually " non-merged " sections optics and magnetism departments between connection the first there is observed

Faraday event observation in order to of an electromagnet poles between magnet in terms of asset didn't happen substance (K), for example a piece of glass let's put Initially polarizer (P) and of the analyzer (A). polarization plains mutually

² M AGNITOOPTIKA VChERA I SEGODNYa (k 170-letiyu discovery effect Faraday) - A. N. Verhozin . Vestnik Pskovskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. UDC 537.632

perpendicular by doing we place , i.e initial without on the screen light light appear it won't be .

From this after , being studied to substance (K) . electromagnetic outline through magnet strength lines effect show starts Linear polarized * light the light from glass so we will spend it light and magnet field strength lines one in the direction to be we provide . K substance polarization plane turn to see it is possible turning usual methods with observed and is measured .

of the event quantitative laws Faraday found being , him one series Verde is fuller in bodies touched

Faraday -Verde law : polarization of the plain turning angle – ϕ , light in substance of the road length - l to magnet of the area induction - to B right is proportional .

$$\phi = VB l \tag{1}$$

where the V-Verde constant is . Verde constant being observed substance type , electromagnetic light frequency and to the temperature depends . Above to the law according to magnet field under the influence of everyone bodies polarization plane very small corner even if it changes .

Polarization of the plane turning the corner Faraday effect according to changing the light intensity $I = I_0 \cos^2 \phi$ – Malyus to the law according to change it we can and this light its rays modulation * enable will give .

To experiments according to too many in substances polarization plane right to the side , that is electromagnetic wraps wrapped towards becomes (in this the light magnet area direction across we observe) . Such substances positive called

substances , however some one paramagnetic in substances polarization plane to the left becomes , such substances Minus called substances . That's it in mind storage should each of the body rotate direction magnet field direction depends of light spread direction depends it won't be .

Faraday of the effect classic Description : Fresnel's to his opinion according to light of light polarization plane of light *circular hesitating fracture* as a result will change was Linear polarized the light two half amplitude left and right polarized to the rays separate can In that case from substance past light polarization of the plain turning corner to the following equal to will be :

$$\varphi = \frac{\pi l}{\lambda_0} (n_{chap} - n_{omg}) \quad (2)$$

in this l – optical asset environment length ;

λ_0 – light of light in a vacuum wave length ;

n_{left} , n_{right} - "left" and " right " waves break down indicator .

n_{left} and n_{right} indicators equal to that it is not due to " right " and "left" waves in the environment different at speeds spreads . Magnet on the field is located optical asset in the environment of the wave corner speeds difference :

$$\Delta\omega = \frac{eB}{m_e} \quad (3)$$

e is an electron charge , m_e – electron mass , B is constant magnet field induction .

of the environment optical light break down indicator to frequency dependent , ie in the environment *dispersion* observed .

$$n_{chap} - n_{o'ng} = \frac{dn}{d\omega} \Delta\omega = \frac{dn}{d\omega} \frac{eB}{m_e} \quad (4)$$

(1.53) in the formula $\lambda_0 = \frac{2\pi c}{\omega}$ from being

$$\varphi = \frac{l}{2c} \omega \frac{dn}{d\omega} \frac{eB}{m_e} \quad (5)$$

the harvest we do (1.56) from the formula found expression (1.51) into the formula , V_n – Verde 's normal constant we find

$$V_n(\omega, T) = \frac{e}{2m_e c} \omega \frac{dn}{d\omega} \quad (6)$$

Above relationship Beckerl is called the formula .

Zeeman effect : Faraday's the first magneto - optical 50 years since its discovery then in 1896 Zeeman external magnet field under the influence of spectral lines of frequency weak to change discover did Faraday in 1862 spent of experience schematic device of the Zeeman device principle to the structure suitable will come . This is it in experience Faraday sodium vapors of the spectrum magnet field under the influence of to change to observe trying saw However separate spectral apparatus get of ability low and magnet of the field weakness as a result spectral of lines change not observed . Zeeman spectral of lines from change except Lawrence to the instruction according to spectral of lines polarization also observed the characteristics .

of cadmium very narrow green - blue the line in observation , one 10,000-15,000 E magnet field harvest do it will receive electromagnetic poles between linear spectrum giving Geisler pipe or vacuum arc is placed . Longitudinal effect (magnetic the field field across observation) record to do for electromagnetic core piercing is placed . Light separate get ability big has been (about 100,000) . diffraction fence or interference to the spectroscope is lowered (in the drawing S_p). Coming out light the light polarization feature analysis to do for light L – lens , N – analyzer and a quarter wavy plate will be placed .

Magnet field when not whose frequency is n the most simple spectral lines , for example H, Zn, Cd in observation spectral lines of frequencies change as follows :

Magnet on the field field across (doublet) – $n- Dn$ and $n+Dn$.

Magnet on the field to the field transversely (triplet) – $n- Dn$, n , $n+Dn$.

Lawrence to the law according to magnet θ velocity in the field with moving to a particle field by effect doer force : $F = q \cdot B \cdot \theta \cdot \sin a$

q is a particle charge quantity , B – magnetic field induction

α - $\vec{v}$ and $\vec{B}$ vectors between angle. First case ($\alpha = 0^\circ$), magnet moving parallel to the field to the electron field by never how strength effect does not because $\sin \alpha = 0$.

Figure 1 : Light of light elliptical polarization described Light scattering direction Z axis across up direction

Second and the third cases ($\alpha = 90^\circ$), magnetic to the field upright moving to the electron field by additional $\pm eB\hbar$ strength direction of electronic movement curvature radius across curve line to the center or to him opposite - opposite directed without effect does Square across to be done oscillating motion is unchanged , the first n frequency with continue is enough

Kerr effect : If linear polarized light light magnetized substance to the surface fall down from him if he returns light light polarization of the plain turning observed . In this light light intensity changed without , elliptic polarized remains . This is it physicist events Keer is called the effect .

Keer's polar effect :

Keer's polar in effect external magnet little one or magnetism example to the plane upright is located being both in this (p and p) polarizations observation can Light of light to the surface upright in falling much better effect observed and magnet conductivity tensor ϵ_{ij} , twist θ , ellipticity πs depends simple equation with is determined . If the light beam Z axis across spreading if :

$$\tilde{\Phi} = \vartheta + i\Psi = \frac{i\epsilon_{xy}}{\hat{n}(\epsilon_{xx} - 1)}$$

$\hat{n} = n + ik$ - complex break down indicator .

Above to Eq according to dielectric permeability tensor always real from componenta consists of was , devourer didn't happen environments returned light polarization of the plain turning not observed . External field under the influence of Keer effect linear , twist of the corner hint while to magnetism looking changed stands Ferromagnet didn't happen substances for this effect sometimes “ returned in the rays Faraday's polar " effect " is also called .

Keer's meridional (meridional) effect :

This is it effect Keer's longitudinally or meridional also known as the effect . Magnetization vector returning surface plane across , descending light light is located parallel to the plane . Get off of the corner big values this effect better manifestation will be

Keer's equatorial effect :

This is it effect Keer's transversely also known as effector . Keer's equatorial in effect magnetism descender light light to the plane perpendicular , sample is located parallel to the plane . This is it effect polarization of the component to magnetism upright has been in the situation observed (p – component), case parallel to magnetization for to zero equal (s – component). Keer's equatorial effect the first in order magnetism is an effector . Substance repetition of the coefficient magnetism under the influence of change as a result light intensity will change and linear polarized light light phase shift observed . This is it effector only devourer substances , that is dielectric permeability of the tensor complex part to zero equal to didn't happen in materials observed . Dielectric permeability of the tensor real in values and polarized in s- components of light very weak quadratic effect observed .

of magnetization non-linear effect : Polar , meridional and equatorial to effects addition respectively polarization of the plain to magnetism connection has been quadratic effects are also available . This is it effect Keer's quadratic called the effect , Vogt and Cotton -Muton effects with to us known .

Magneto-optical environments :

Electromagnet to the wave to the effect according to , magneto-optical materials two to class is divided .

First class in the materials magneto-optical effect magnet of the field to electron orbital motion effect does (Zeeyman effect). This is it to class diamagnets and diamagnetism always there is has been one bullet symmetrical transparent substances enters In this observable magneto-optical effects very weak will be

Second class to the materials ferromagnet substances and low temperature metal didn't happen paramagnetic substances enters This is it in substances magneto-optical effects magnet of the field electron spin-orbital movement effect as a result to the body will come .

Magnetism to the light effect does , but this effect usually very is small . How by doing magnet field the light manage can Answer clear : magneto-optical of effects efficiency increase need.

Summary.

In the article books analysis from him except physicist processes in expression which uses main concepts in particular , crystallographic in the structure symmetry arrows , hard of bodies symmetry of arrows review , drawings , Miller indices and their hard bodies in particular of magnetics parameters in expression the importance of crystals magnet of sorting theoretical basics , electronic structures , shells , ferromagnets , antiferromagnets and ferrite substances , their harvest to be of the conditions physical description , in ferrites domain borders and their harvest to be , domain structures structures , magneto-optical events and hard your bodies magneto-optics , magnet and optics departments mutually shortness of breath present modern technological in development importance about considerations giving went.

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